

International Journal of Advances in Engineering & Scientific Research (IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 -3607 (Online)

ISSN: 2349 -4824 (Print)

Available online at:

<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-4-aug-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and
subscription information:

<http://www.arseam.com/>

PASSIVE COOLING METHODS FOR ENERGY EFFICIENT BUILDING COLOUR EFFECT

Abid Ali Nagra¹, Dr. PBL Chaurasia² and Mr.P.N.Mathur³

1. M.Tech Research Scholar

2. Dean Engg. Suresh GyanVihar University, Jaipur

3. HOD of civil department, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur

Centre Of Excellence, Solar Energy Research & Utilization,
Suresh GyanVihar University, Jaipur

Abstract

Heat absorption is defined as the movement of heat by means of radiation, convection, or conduction. Color is defined as a visual perceptual property. In the comparison of heat absorption vs. color, what is perceived as a simple color is actual various frequencies of light. When presenting a dark color in a heavily heated environment, individuals are actually attracting a higher amount of light frequencies than they would with a light color. The exact opposite applies when presenting a light color in a heavily heated environment. In this case, light colors attract less light frequencies, which make them a better choice when attempting to maintain coolness to heat

Keywords: Natural cooling, Passive cooling, Techniques, climatic design, energy conservation.

URBAN HEAT ISLAND EFFECT

The urban heat island effect, we first need to understand a few simple rules of physics. Most importantly, we should understand that objects can absorb and reflect light. In fact, the colour of an object depends on what kind of light it reflects. For example, a green object reflects green light and absorbs all the other visible colours of light. When we see a green object, we perceive it as green because it reflects the green wavelength of colour back to our eyes. Darker coloured objects

are excellent absorbers of light. In fact, black surfaces absorb almost all light. On the other hand, lighter coloured surfaces do not absorb much light at all -- rather they reflect almost all of it.

So what does the absorption of light have to do with heat? When an object absorbs light, it converts that light to thermal energy, and emits it back out as heat. So, because black objects absorb more light, they also emit more heat. That's why wearing a black shirt on a hot, sunny day will only make you hotter. The black shirt absorbs light and emits it as heat onto your skin. Wearing a white shirt, on the other hand, will help reflect the sunlight and keep you cooler.

The rate at which an object can reflect solar radiation is called its **albedo**. The bigger the albedo something has, the better it reflects radiation. Traditional asphalt has a low albedo, which means it reflects radiation poorly and instead absorbs it.

When we build and expand cities, we tend to erect buildings with dark surfaces and lay down asphalt pavement. The buildings and the pavement absorb a significant amount of light and radiation and emit it as heat, warming the city. Because more than half of the surfaces in cities are man-made, cities heat up more than rural areas, where structures are less concentrated. This heat absorption is why the temperature difference between cities and rural areas is highest a few hours after sunset. Cities hold on to more heat for a longer period of time than rural areas do

But that's not the only thing that causes the urban heat island effect. Scientists believe that vegetation plays a large part in keeping an area cool through a process called evaporative cooling. **Evaporation** is when liquid turns into gas. Plants take in water through their roots and depend on it to live. But after the plant is done with it, dry air absorbs that water by turning it into gaseous **water vapour**. The air provides the heat that drives this process, so during the process, the air loses heat and becomes cooler. We experience the same type of thing when we sweat -- when air hits your sweaty skin, it absorbs the moisture and cools the air around you. Because building a city means replacing vegetation with structures, the city loses the evaporative cooling advantages of vegetation.

Applications

Unfortunately dark coloured roofs soak up the Sun's energy getting hotter and hotter as the day progresses. When the roof space becomes superheated at up to 90°C on a 35°C day, the temperature

of rooms below can become unbearable even with insulation. Air conditioning is overworked and temperature extremes detrimentally affect the durability and longevity of the whole roof structure. Given the effect dark roof colours have on interior house temperature, it is surprising that dark colours make up more than 75% of the colours used in our suburbs. Insulation helps, although once the heat is inside the roof space, ceiling insulation only delays the heat transfer process.

The best method is to prevent the roof space heating up in the first place, by reflecting heat away from the roof surface. If the surface of the roof is prevented from getting very hot the rooms below are kept cooler reducing cooling costs due to lower air conditioning energy consumption over the life time of the building

Keeping your home cool in hot weather is also becoming increasingly expensive due to rising energy costs, servicing and maintenance.

White, light pastel and silver roofs have always been the best colours for the Indian environment, because they reflect the Sun's heat. However these colours are not always complimentary to house design. In some cases light coloured and reflective roofs are not permitted by Council planning controls. These controls are intended to prevent glare for neighbours and for improved visual aesthetics.

References

1. White Roofs May Successfully Cool Cities: Computer Model Simulates Impact of White Roofs on Urban Areas. Posted January 28, 2010. Press release 10-016, National Science Foundation News.http://www.nsf.gov/news/news_summ.jsp?cntn_id=116283
2. Do Different Colors Absorb Heat Better? Grades PreK-2. Education Resources Information Center. Office for Technology and Industry Collaboration, Tufts University and Department of Education. (alternate online location for activity) http://www.eric.ed.gov/ERICWebPortal/search/detailmini.jsp?_nfpb=true&_ERICExtSearch_SearchValue_0=ED480661&ERICExtSearch_SearchType_0=no&accno=ED480661
Richards, Roy. An Early Start to Technology from Science. London, UK: Simon & Schuster, 1990, page 64.
3. Cool Roof Resources for Federal Agencies. Federal Energy Management Guide, U.S. Department of Energy. http://www1.eere.energy.gov/femp/features/cool_roof_resources.html